

Thermal Performance of a Latent Heat Storage (LHS) Prototype for the ECHO Project

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Abstract

Thermal energy storage (TES) is a strategic solution to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and increase renewable energy penetration. Latent heat storage (LHS) is growing in importance thanks to its higher energy density compared to sensible heat technologies. However, phase change materials (PCMs) still suffer from limitations such as subcooling, phase separation and low thermal conductivity, requiring encapsulation techniques and addition of nanoparticles or metal foams.

In this context, the Horizon Europe project ECHO is developing a hybrid TES system for residential applications, that combines PCMs with an innovative thermochemical material (TCM). The TCM is charged in a reactor through dehydration, while heat is discharged to the user through the material hydration, supplying space heating and domestic hot water. During the discharging phase, the humid air entering the TCM reactor is preheated through a LHS tank containing a macroencapsulated PCM immersed in a heat transfer fluid.

This study presents the results of laboratory testing of the LHS prototype, which consisted of a 59-litre tank containing five vertical tubes filled with the selected commercial paraffin-based PCM (declared phase change temperature of 32 °C). The PCM was also characterised through differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and T-history analyses and the prototype's thermal performance was investigated through repeated solidification and melting cycles. Furthermore, thermography tests were carried out to test the insulation of the tank.

The experimental results demonstrate the feasibility and efficiency of the LHS design under realistic operating conditions, providing useful data for the following design of the full-scale system.

1. Introduction

Achieving the Paris agreement's objectives [1] requires a strong commitment to decrease greenhouse gas emissions, both increasing efficiency and renewable energy integration.

A focus on the buildings sector is crucial, since in 2023 it accounted for 32 % of the total energy consumption and 34 % of CO₂ emissions [2]. In this framework, thermal energy storage (TES) emerges as a versatile solution for decarbonising the heating and cooling sector. As all storage technologies, it allows to decouple the energy supply and demand and to shift the load, reducing peaks and addressing renewable energy unpredictability [3], [4]. Furthermore, TES is competitive thanks to its lower cost and higher availability of materials compared, for example, to electric batteries.

Many TES technologies have been developed and are being studied by researchers, including a wide range of materials and different configurations. They are usually classified as:

- Sensible heat storage (SHS), which exploits the temperature variation of the material or fluid. This technology is the most mature, simple and commercialised [5], especially with water as medium, but has the lowest energy density and is affected by high heat losses.
- Latent heat storage (LHS), which is based on the melting and solidification at constant temperature of phase change materials (PCM). These are usually distinguished among inorganic, organic and eutectic PCMs.
- Thermochemical storage (TCS), which stores and releases heat through reversible chemical reactions, with the highest values of energy density and allowing to store heat without losses for long-term periods [6].

In the past years, LHS was the subject of the majority of research publications on TES [7], and interest in this technology continues to grow due to the higher energy density compared to SHS and the easier feasibility compared to TCS. Nevertheless, significant limitations still affect PCMs: organic materials are mainly affected by low thermal conductivity and flammability, while inorganic PCMs suffer from incongruent transition and subcooling and can be corrosive [8]. Among organic PCMs, paraffin is widely used in the building sector. It is a mixture of hydrocarbons usually derived from petroleum products [9]. Enhancement strategies for thermal conductivity include macro and microencapsulation, finned surfaces, and addition of nanoparticles and metal foams [10]. Encapsulation techniques improve flexibility, heat transfer and stability of PCMs, and are particularly suitable for organic materials [11]. Macroencapsulation is a simple way to exploit these advantages, and consists of containers of size > 1 mm. However, the enhancement of performance is limited compared to micro- and nano- techniques [12]. In the framework of advancing and innovating TES systems, the Horizon Europe project

ECHO (Efficient Compact Modular Thermal Energy Storage System) is developing a hybrid system consisting on the application of both PCMs and an innovative thermochemical material (TCM), which is arranged in drawers stacked in a reactor [13]. The TCM releases energy when dehydrated by humid air, and it charges through dehydration. The air entering the reactor preheats by flowing through a heat exchanger connected to a LHS system, consisting of a paraffin-based PCM macroencapsulated in vertical tubes inserted in a tank.

This study analyses the results of experimental tests both on the selected PCM, to evaluate its properties, and on a laboratory scale prototype of the LHS tank, analysing the charging and discharging behaviour and investigating the effectiveness of the thermal insulation. Rather than characterising the material, the main objective is to evaluate the performance of the prototype in terms of peak power and exchanged energy, making the collected data available for the design of the scaled-up system for the three ECHO demo sites. Furthermore, this work investigates a LHS configuration seldom seen in literature, i.e. including paraffin encapsulated in vertical tubes in a tank. Indeed, in the “shell-and-tube-like” configurations studied in literature so far, the heat transfer fluid (HTF) is often inside the tubes and the PCM outside, and not vice versa. Gasia et al. [14] characterised the commercial paraffin RT58 both at laboratory scale and in a shell-and-tube heat exchanger in a pilot plant, detecting a phase change temperature range of 50-61 °C and an enthalpy of 120.11 kJ/kg. The PCM is suitable for use up to 80 °C and withstood 1200 cycles without degradation. Kirincic et al. [15] tested the paraffin PCM RT25 during the melting process in a shell-and-tube heat exchanger, observing the increase of the melting rate with higher HTF inlet temperature. This aspect was evaluated also by Zhang et al. [16], who experimentally studied a composite paraffin tank with an immersed spiral tube. Xiao & Zhang [17], [18] developed an enthalpy-based model for comparing pure paraffin and two graphite-enhanced composites, validating the results with experimental tests. They observed faster charging and discharging processes with high mass flow rates and temperature difference between HTF and PCM, and enhanced thermal conductivity in the case of the composite PCMs, with almost half of the time required for phase change. Shen et al. [19] compared both experimentally and numerically a multi-tube and a single-tube LHS systems, with the HTF flowing in the tubes. The configuration with five tubes allowed a 50 % reduction of the charging and

discharging time with respect to considering only two tubes. An increase in the HTF temperature reduced both the phase change periods, while an increase in the flow rate affected more the charging process.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. PCM characterisation

The PCM and tank configuration were selected within the framework of the ECHO project. Salt hydrates were excluded due to issues related to subcooling and stability, and therefore the organic PCM A32 was selected. A32 is a commercial paraffin purchased from PCM Products Ltd. [20], with a declared phase change temperature of 32 °C (Table 1), suitable for the intended application.

Table 1. Properties of A32 from PCM Products Ltd. [20].

A32	Phase change Temperature (°C)	Density (kg m ⁻³)	Latent heat capacity (kJ kg ⁻¹)	Volumetric heat capacity (MJ m ⁻³)	Specific Heat capacity (kJ kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	Thermal conductivity (W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	Maximum operating temperature (°C)
	32	845	120	101	2.2	0.121	200

The material was characterised through differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and T-history method. DSC analyses were performed with a TA Instruments SDT-Q600, with a calorimetric accuracy of ±2 % based on metal standards. Temperature scans were set at 2 °C/min around the phase change temperature, and each measurement was repeated for 20 melting/solidification cycles. The T-history method [21] was applied to measure the properties of 28·10⁻⁶ m³ sample of A32 encapsulated in vertical high-density polyethylene (HDPE) cylindrical vials (diameter of 0.023 m, height of 0.070 m, wall thickness of 0.001 m). The cooling profile of the encapsulated PCM was measured and compared with that of water, under identical natural air conditions, cooling from 44 °C to 2–22 °C. Melting profiles were obtained by allowing the samples to fully solidify at room temperature (20 –22 °C), followed by heating at 45 °C in a thermostatic bath. K-type thermocouples were inserted at the centre of each vial. The stability of A32 was assessed through periodical repetitions of the melting/solidification cycles.

2.2. Lab-scale set-up

The lab-scale set-up was similar to that described by Lombardo et al., who tested a LHS storage for cooling applications [22]. The LHS tank consisted of a 59-litre stainless steel cylindrical tank, containing 5 vertical polyvinyl chloride (PVC) tubes filled with A32 and sealed by polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) caps. The remaining volume was filled with the HTF, a 70/30 wt.% mixture of double-distilled water and ethylene glycol, circulated through a pump. The involved volumes and the dimensions of the LHS storage are summarised in Table 2. The vertical configuration was chosen to occupy less space and keep the whole ECHO system more compact, despite the increased influence of gravity on the phase change process. A thermostatic bath (thermal control stability = ± 0.02 K) regulated the temperature of the HTF, and a magnetic flowmeter (uncertainty = ± 0.04 % FS, full scale 600 l/s) measured the volume flow rate. The bath provides up to 2 kW of heating power and 0.42–0.6 kW of cooling power within the -10 °C to 100 °C range. The experimental set-up is shown in Figure 1, with part of the thermal insulation visible. The tank was externally insulated using polyurethane (PU) panels enhanced with butyl stearate (onset and peak temperatures at 17.74 °C and 20.37 °C respectively) as PCM, developed by the Technical University of Istanbul and manufactured by Ideakim©. The thickness of the insulation was 0.05 m, with a 15 wt.% PCM content and a thermal conductivity equal to 0.043 W m⁻¹ K⁻¹).

Table 2. Dimensions of the prototype.

	Volume (L)	Dimensions* (m)
Cylindrical tank	59	$h = 0.9, d_e = 0.3, t = 0.002$
PCM in tubes	6.4	$h = 1, d_e = 0.05$
Water/glycol mixture outside tubes	50	-

*h = height, d_e = external diameter, t = thickness

Figure 1. Picture of the tank with PVC tubes visible (left) and closed with partial insulation (right).

The tests consisted of three charging/discharging cycles, setting the bath temperature to 40 °C for melting and 20 °C for solidification, and operating the pump at a constant speed of 3500 rpm. To monitor the temperature both inside the HTF and the PCM, eleven K-type thermocouples (T1 to T11) and two Class A Pt100 resistance temperature detectors were positioned as shown in Figure 2. The layout of the thermocouples was chosen to investigate eventual radial and vertical gradients. Taking advantage of the symmetry of the tank, only three tubes were equipped with sensor. T5 was placed in the lowest position, 0.07 m from the bottom of the tube, T6 at mid-height, and T7, T9 and T11 were positioned at the top, 0.15 m from the cap. T8 and T10 were placed horizontally off-centre, near the tube wall, 0.2 m from the cap. The sensors were connected to an Agilent 34970A data acquisition system, with measurement uncertainties of ± 0.1 K for the thermocouples and ± 0.07 K for the Pt100 sensors. Data were acquired every 15 seconds and monitored and save through a LabVIEW interface.

Figure 2. Positioning of the sensors: red dots represent thermocouples in the PCM, blue dots the thermocouples in the HTF, green dots the Pt100 sensor.

Furthermore, a FLIR SC660 infrared (IR) camera acquired IR images of the tank every five minutes, to evaluate the efficacy of the thermal insulation. The specifications of the camera are reported in Table 3. Two tests without insulation were also carried out, as a comparison. A Class A Pt100 sensor (uncertainty = 0.2 K) positioned next to the tank recorded the air temperature every five minutes.

Table 3 Specifications for the SC660 IR camera.

Thermal sensitivity	≤45 mK
Spectral range	7.5 – 13 μm
Spatial resolution	640 x 480 pixels
Accuracy	±2 °C or ±2 % of reading

2.3. Data processing and uncertainty analysis

For each charging/discharging cycle, thermal power (P) and exchanged energy (E) on the HTF side were calculated using Eq. 1-2, based on measurements of volume flow rate and inlet and outlet temperatures at each timestep (τ). The obtained values were averaged over the three tests repetitions for both melting and solidification. The specific heat and density of the HTF at each measurement point were computed through the empirical correlations presented in Eq. 3-4, based on regression of data from Ref. [23].

$$P = \rho \dot{V}_{HTF} c_{p,HTF} \Delta T_{HTF} \quad (1)$$

$$E = P \tau \quad (2)$$

$$c_p = -0.000003 t_{in}^3 - 0.008694 t_{in}^2 + 3.388932 t_{in} + 3684.155668 \quad (3)$$

$$\rho = -0.000012 t_{in}^3 - 0.003994 t_{in}^2 - 0.268936 t_{in} + 1045.329384 \quad (4)$$

The energy exchange was evaluated over the phase change interval, defined by the thermocouple with the slowest phase change transition (T5 during melting and T6 during solidification). This timeframe was used to estimate latent heat and compare with the DSC measurement.

For each thermocouple's temperature profile, the duration of each phase change process was determined graphically using the tangent method, which identifies intersection points between tangents drawn along the pre- and post-transition linear sections and the transition region itself.

The uncertainty analysis followed the JCGM guidelines [24]. The combined standard uncertainty u_c derived from type A and type B (when available from the manufacturer) uncertainties was calculated for each measured quantity by combining Type A (u_A) and

Type B (u_B) components (Eq. 5). The uncertainty propagation law was applied as in Eq. 6-7. The expanded uncertainty for power was then obtained by multiplying the standard uncertainty by a coverage factor $k = 2$, corresponding to a 95.45 % confidence level.

$$u_c = \sqrt{u_A^2 + u_B^2} \quad (5)$$

$$u(\Delta T) = \sqrt{[u(T_{in})]^2 + [u(T_{out})]^2} \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{u(P)}{P} = \sqrt{\left[\frac{u(\dot{V})}{\dot{V}}\right]^2 + \left[\frac{u(\Delta T)}{\Delta T}\right]^2 + \left[\frac{u(c_p)}{c_p}\right]^2 + \left[\frac{u(\rho)}{\rho}\right]^2} \quad (7)$$

3. Results and discussion

3.1. DSC and T-history of the PCM

The results of the DSC analysis are presented in Figure 3 and summarised in Table 4. The melting onset and peak were detected at 28.72 °C and 31.69 °C respectively. The 20 performed cycles were almost overlapping, demonstrating optimal cyclability. The measured gravimetric latent heat was 28 % higher than the manufacturer’s specification, highlighting the importance of conducting characterisation measurements also on commercial products. Given the accuracy of the DSC methodology, the measured value has been taken as reference for the measurements in the prototype.

Figure 3. DSC analysis for A32 (top: detail of one cycle; bottom: 20 cycles).

Table 4 Results of the DSC analysis.

Grav. Latent Heat (2 K min⁻¹)	165 kJ kg ⁻¹
Vol. Latent Heat (2 K min⁻¹)	139 MJ m ⁻³
Subcooling (peak to peak)	2 °C
Cyclability	Very good

T-history measurements identified a phase change temperature of 30.7 °C (Figure 4). Over the course of 192 cycles, the estimated latent heat remained stable at around 230 kJ kg⁻¹, about 28 % higher than that measured with DSC. This discrepancy likely derives from the inherent difficulty in accurately defining the end point of the solidification process. An initial 9 % deviation observed in the first cycle was due to differences in ambient conditions: the room air temperature was 23 °C during the first cycle and 20 °C for cycles 27 through 192. This temperature DSC difference was accounted for in the calculation of the latent heat.

Figure 4. T-history measurement and latent heat estimation for A32.

3.2. Tests on lab-scale prototype and thermography

The temperature profiles recorded during charging (melting) and discharging (solidification) processes are depicted in Figure 5. A distinct phase change plateau was evident during the solidification process, with no signs of subcooling. On the other hand, the melting process lacked a clear phase change transition, probably due to the composition of A32, which is a mixture of different paraffin components and since the bottom part of the tubes was the first to be exposed to the hot HTF, and therefore the higher density of the solid phase at the top made it migrate towards the bottom under the effect of gravity, making the process inhomogeneous. Moreover, natural convection accelerates the melting process of PCMs, which therefore is usually faster than solidification [25]. These aspects hindered a precise evaluation of the transition time interval, and consequently the calculation of the related energy exchanged. Therefore, the phase change timeframes were different for charging and discharging (Table 5). This led to an underestimation of the energy exchanged during melting, computed as 126 kJ kg^{-1} , 24 % lower than the latent heat value measured by DSC. On the other hand, the discharged energy was estimated as 390 kJ kg^{-1} , 136 % higher than the measured latent heat value. This is explained because the considered timeframe is related to

the thermocouple detecting the longest phase change transition, inevitably including a portion of sensible heat exchanged in correspondence of the positions of the other thermocouples in the tubes, characterised by a faster transition process.

Figure 5 includes also the tank shell (without insulation) temperature profiles acquired by the IR camera, showing consistency with the measurements inside the tank.

Figure 5. Temperature profiles during charging (top) and discharging (bottom) of the LHS tank. The dotted temperature profiles refer to the thermography measurements. “Bottom”, “mid” and “top” refer to the height of the points in the tank’s surface considered in the thermography tests.

Table 5 Results of the charging-discharging cycles.

	Charging (melting)	Discharging (solidification)
Maximum phase change time (hh:mm)	00:45	01:38
Average phase change time (hh:mm)	n.a.	00:57
Peak power (W)	284	523
Average power (W)	$96 \pm 0.68^*$	$182 \pm 0.67^*$

*Maximum expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$).

The performance of the insulation is demonstrated in Figure 6, where the HTF temperature was raised from $-10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, to test the insulation performance also at lower temperature. The temperature of the insulation remained almost constant for the entire duration of the test.

Figure 6. Temperature profiles of the insulation and inside the tank for a test with the HTF increasing its temperature from $-10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The dashed lines refer to the external surface temperature of the insulation, measured by the IR camera.

4. Conclusions and future work

This work investigated the performance of a lab-scale LHS prototype with a shell-and-tube configuration, employing the organic PCM A32. The study combined material characterisation, through DSC and T-history, with experimental testing of three charging/discharging cycles to assess the system's thermal behaviour.

DSC measured a latent heat of 165 kJ kg^{-1} , which was taken as a reference due to the higher accuracy of the instrument. A value 28 % higher was estimated from T-history measurements, while the charging and discharging tests on the prototype led to a 24 % underestimation and a 58 % overestimation respectively. These discrepancies are attributed to the difficulties in precisely isolating the phase change transition. On average, the LHS tank discharged 0.56 kWh over a period of 1 hour and 38 minutes. Further charging and discharging tests of the prototype are planned in the following months, to test its performance enhancement by inserting brass foams in the PCM. Preliminary small-scale tests performed within the framework of the ECHO project have already shown promising results, with a thermal conductivity enhancement of 86 % compared to pure paraffin [26]. Finally, thermography tests demonstrated the efficacy of the PU-PCM thermal insulation for this application. The results presented in this study will be used as relevant input data for the design of the scaled-up LHS storage tank, to be installed in the demo sites of the ECHO project.

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